

De-Creation of Creation, or A New Level of Culture in the Development of *homo*

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ABSTRACT

Wolfgang Sassin. *De-Creation of Creation, or A New Level of Culture in the Development of homo.* The public discussion at the beginning of the twenty-first century reveals much about a supposed conflict with nature, about the motifs behind the vehemently demanded change of the industrial civilization and about the dawning of a new world of the digital. Together they touch the very basis of a complex civilization supporting nearly eight billion people at the price of a fundamentally changed "creation." Ongoing efforts to overcome all spatial and temporal distances, thereby dissolving existing orders in space and time and populating the world with Artificial Intelligence, raise the question whether *homo sapiens* is aiming to occupy the realm of gods, if not of the One and Only in order to guarantee the survival of human kind.

Key words: humanity, civilisation, history of human society, agriculture, farming, hunting, gathering, industry, artificial intelligence, globalisation, monotheism, mono-humanism, monotheistic religions, religious ideology

CONTINUING DOMESTICATION OF *HOMO SAPIENS*

ABOUT 5000 YEARS AGO, agriculture not only set itself apart from the “culture” of hunters and gatherers; from the very beginning it was in conflict with the archaic principle of appropriating what was available – mostly with little effort, but usually with violence. The more closely man observed nature and the more concealed the acquired knowledge and the exercise of power made possible by it could be organised, the easier it was to take prey and determine its distribution. The only obstacle was the proximity of other groups, against which one had to arm oneself if they came too close and claimed what nature offered or what “the others” had laboriously created.

The principle of subduing the world has survived to our times. In a highly elaborate form it has managed to rise via aristocracy, royalty and empires up to the modern “democratically” legitimised welfare state. And it has contributed to establish domestication up to the point of enslavement as the normal state of “advanced” human societies. This trend is clearly heading towards the global level. It aims at an all-embracing system of minute control of the individual, wherever he might live and how difficult it might be to “include” him. The declared objective is to maximise the total human potential by raising standards and pushing “development,” in order to be able to skim results and to distribute them “just” and global.

Figure 1, designed in the framework of classical values, therefore distracts from the **actually prevailing situation**. The culture of hunting and gathering is dominating as ever. It has subjugated cattle breeding, agriculture and industrial production and in this process it is now using the instruments of the digital age to subject not only the earth, but as many homos as possible, hopefully all.

Fig. 1. The development of civilisations by men.

It is in line with this principle that ever more "powerful" economic organizations did rise and expand, particularly so once they had discovered information and communication as

their most profitable field of business. This last stage of cultural "ascent" did not take millennia, however. A few start-ups emerged into global players within the last two to three decades. All societal organisations, in the entire spectrum from dictatorial to democratic, are struggling to appropriate this new instrument of "exploitation" in order to monitor "their" subjects, to control them meticulously and to skim off their "achievements," in order to further domesticate *homo sapiens*, unswervingly declared as "free," and to make him more "social" and "human" as a member of masses.

Fig. 2. Change in *homo sapiens* as a result of its civilisation development.

The situation in the 21st century therefore develops differently than is generally perceived. Fig. 1 graphically follows the simple Zeitgeist. But let us do not be tempted by the "success stories" that suggest differential considerations, those considerations that politicians, economists and historians adore to use if they define progress as the sum of tiny steps "in the right" direction and thus "making history." Fig. 2 more accurately illustrates the actual consequences of human endeavours.

SO WHERE ARE WE ACTUALLY HEADING?

DOES THE INDIVIDUAL HAVE TO BECOME A CELL OF A "GOOD" GLOBAL ORGANISM, within perhaps one or two further generations? Is he reduced to a centrally controlled cell for the conversion of energy and information that serves a "whole" pretending to shape the planet and reaching out into space to observe everyone from above without exception?

Should each of these specialised cells be activated according to a grand plan, or neutralised in the case of insubordination, if they elude the emotional and logical specifications of an autistic elite, for example because they multiply at their own discretion or seek to pursue “private” goals? What actually happened to the “dropouts” of the last third of the 20th century? Have they not given way to activists who want to “enter” a boundless and “open” world, something that has never existed before?

Are we entering the era of a global culture which sets out to dissolve all forms of existing cultures, from hunting and gathering, via locally and regionally adapted farming to industrial production depending on highly unequally distributed natural exhaustible and renewable resources, and which subjects them all to a global redistribution and recycling administration?

Such an economically motivated “administration” of the “well-being” of mankind negates fundamental geographical, climatic, ecological and cultural differences (Donskikh 2019b).

Fig. 2. Moses and Aaron before the Pharaoh. An engraving of Gustave Doré.
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It is dissolving established values and it believes that it can make the fruits of a universal economic exchange accessible to all people and that it is even obliged to do so based on the notion of a justice defined as all-embracing. The technically created possibilities of being able to overcome spatial distances almost at will seduce almost everyone to the naïve idea that living conditions, in particular the possibilities of consumption, must therefore be standardised and equalised everywhere in the world. The apologists of globalization thus attempt to “replace” the previously direct and very differentiated close relationships between humans and those between humans and nature by virtual zero-distance relationships; a process leading to general and profound alienation. For the sake of peace and justice, it is said, it must be made clear to each individual that he/she/it must share and react to the fate of any other individual on this planet. Nothing else is inherent in any living organism

that reacts as a whole to the stimulus of any part of its body. How sensitive and how inflexible and immobile would such a *United Humanity* be?

Are we facing a *Hybrid Society* in which *Big Brother*, realised in the form of algorithms and a densely networked communication infrastructure, an omnipresent two-way “social media system,” determines what each “individual cell” would have to do and to avoid, including its sacrifice if necessary? The trend towards the dissolution of all kinds of borders, the dissolution of cultural niches, even the conviction that there is a “right” acquired by birth to participate in this crease-free, i.e. simple-minded paradise with standardised living conditions, taken together they characterise the postmodern Western *Zeitgeist*. It ignores the resulting indispensable necessity of such an “organism” to force each “cell” to specialise on command and to remain on the spot and to willingly fulfil the “function” it has been assigned to in one of the different organs of the “whole.” Every functional and spatial deviation of such a “cell” from its place would then be tantamount to “migration” and to the formation of “parallel societies”, terms that are known in the medical field as proliferation and metastasis of “autonomous” cancerous cells. Such “individuality” and such liberties of the individual must, logically compelling, obviously be prevented under all circumstances in order not to endanger the “survival of humanity.”

What would the constitution of a global society, so intensely suggested to us, if not missionarily overturned, look like? Who is trying with all his might today to push through such a constitution, primarily in the form of ever more embracing human rights? For the purpose of global standardisation, the only seemingly objective justification is not really to protect the climate of the planet, but to control it globally. This simply serves as a pretence: Conservation of nature as an absolute purpose in its own right ultimately aims at controlling the ecology of the planet, from protozoa to insects, to largely autonomous meta-systems, such as rain forests or the thermohaline circulation of the oceans which forms the “climate” of aquatic forms of life. In practical terms, however, this would mean nothing less than a meticulous control of man and all his actions.

NEW PROPHETS AND REVELATIONS IN THE SITUATION OF DEFECTIVE PRIVACY

IN VIEW OF THESE VERY REAL PERSPECTIVES and the obvious shrinking private living space triggered by ever more mobile billions that are added per human reproductive cycle, in view of “neighbours” who are moving ever closer in mega-centres and who seek to compensate for the loss of their individuality by constantly growing consumption and ever shorter fashion cycles – in view of this rapid and fundamental change in the living conditions of the individual, general uncertainty is spreading. Such afflicted and depressed people are always susceptible to “revelations” because they no longer understand themselves, their inner life nor their imprisonment to which they themselves have contributed. They search for “prophets,” for people who show them a way out of the mental dilemma of the present into

a future, be it in a dreamed paradisiacal world “on earth” or in transcendence.

How different can the economic theories of an Adam Smith, a Marx, a Keynes or even a Müller-Armack be classified in retrospect, taking into account the proliferating mega-cities and their meanwhile existential dependence on globally distributed complex supply and disposal systems for raw materials, energy and also for information? Their possibilities and limits can no longer be overlooked by a single person. The same applies to all previous models of social organisation, from autocracy to plutocracy to democracy.

The **exhaustion of the *Creation*** deplored by man, in fact a highly complex and constantly changing system of living conditions evolving through trial and error but dogmatised as a predetermined gift of God, raises the question how man could adapt himself to a “nature” modified and permanently “developed” by himself.

The human environment of today is no longer primarily nature but man himself and his conflicting cultures he has developed so far. This „other“ environment is almost impossible to be understood from within a moving herd in which homo sapiens suddenly finds himself. What counts within a herd, particularly at the edge of a stampede, is to keep the necessary distance from one's immediate neighbours and at the same time not to lose ties with “the whole.” Only from a position from “outside” developments can be explained which increasingly manifest themselves as divides of societies, disintegrations of states or unions. Such phenomena, no doubt, are inevitable reactions to the emergence of ever larger, ever more comprehensive and ever more pressing economic and legal spaces.

Whether one looks at the evolution which presents itself as branching and differentiation of species, precisely not as unification and reduction of species diversity, or whether one has the fate of “monocultures” in mind, *homo sapiens* would have to cut his evolutionary roots if he wanted to successfully mutate into a global being

In his book *Principles of Political Economy*, John Stuart Mill wrote some 150 years ago that “social, cultural and moral progress would be all the greater if man were to renounce his addiction to growth.” After this explosive growth triggered by the competition between capitalism and socialism there is no choice but creating a new culture of limiting human quantity as a prerequisite for future human quality. This has nothing to do with saving or renunciation, certainly not with interference in the affairs of third parties. Rather, it presupposes differentiation and evaluation, distance and respect for the “other,” human or not, instead of an extended absolutised humanity, of general equality and of an unlimited interchange and exchange with the aim of achieving growth for its own sake.

Climbing such a new level of culture means nothing less than fundamentally changing those values that threaten to lead us to the exhaustion of a supposed creation. We must recognise hubris as the fundamental deficit of homo sapiens, a property that threatens to bring us down. We repress the final consequences of our thoughts and actions, because as deceased individuals we no longer suffer from them, nor are we able to influence which values our far descendants might ever prefer.

Neither prophets nor saints help in the attempt to gain wisdom through knowledge. The future of *sapiens* does not lie in the transcendental. The occidental “success story” makes

this very clear to us. Only those who are really willing to learn from the past and from their mistakes have a chance in the real world. Adolescents largely lack this option. That is why they dream and play, in the sandpit as in politics, secured by the investments and “assets” of their ancestors and predecessors, but by no means by a benevolent and tolerant creation.

FROM MONOTHEISM TO MONOHUMANISM

A LOOK BACK TO HISTORY makes it clear in what mental dilemma we find ourselves today, but only if this look goes back far enough so that we are not influenced

by our sympathies for other people, people whom we as real people or their immediate descendants might meet and then be forced to take sides for one part or the other and decide what is right or wrong.

The biblical Moses, his likely opponent Amenophis III and his successor, the pharaoh Akhenaten (birth name Amenophis IV), or also a pharaoh after Akhenaten, had similar problems to today's political and spiritual “leaders” with climatic changes, famines, migration caused by the struggle with failed social integration and demographic imbalances. Both feared for their future, in reality for the existential foundations of the communities for which they stood. The fateful challenges against which they had no effective means, mainly because they did not understand their causes, were therefore attributed to displeasing gods.

Fig. 3. Finding of Moses. An engraving of Gustave Doré.
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As a child of the migrants from Canaan, who had sought refuge in Egypt and formed a kind of parallel society there, to whom priests and their gods on the Nile did not sacrifice, and who, due to the lack of other opportunities for advancement in society, increased more quickly than the Egyptians who granted them asylum, Moses escaped as a baby with a scarce need of the “one-child policy” of Pharaoh Amenophis III

(Roberts and Ward 2013, 41–42). Salvaged from the Nile and raised by one of Pharaoh's daughters at the Egyptian court, he learned art of ruling from the political caste, including that of the administrators and the “scientific advisors,” i.e. the priests as guardian of knowledge with prognostic skills (MacArthur 2015, 106).

Given the direct and direct experience of how the guardians dealt with people in the “low-wage sector,” the group he actually came from, Moses got nervous. He abused his courtly position and henceforth depended on the support of those who did early service, but claimed only to serve “their” God as the only one who they believed had created the whole world, including those parts of it the Egyptians claimed for themselves, it was a clear act of psychological self-assertion in an oppressed minority position.

Knowing the practice, Moses skillfully exploited climatic and ecological irregularities to form political opinions at court in order to make Pharaoh believe that his gods had no means against it. And he managed to negotiate the free return to that Canaan where the climatic conditions had just improved again. Amenophis III had underestimated the ability of Moses to lure the Israelites in large numbers to move out of Egypt with the promise that they would find a place to stay in their old home with Jehovah, the creator of heaven and earth and his help, in which, unlike a few generations ago, milk and honey now flow. When the Pharaoh's administrator, his builders and irrigation specialists realized that they were running away from too many cheap workers and the economy of highly developed Egypt was in trouble, Amenophis dispatched his troops. But it was too late. With their horses and heavy chariots, the soldiers were not prepared for the heavy rainfall that meandered the Nile arms of the delta in the eastern Mediterranean, leaving the Israelites free. Arrived in Canaan, after crossing a desert in which water suddenly gushed out of the rocks again due to climatic “irregularities”, and familiar with the knowledge and techniques of Egypt, those “autochtones”

Fig. 4. The Egyptians urge Moses to depart. An engraving of Gustave Doré.

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could be overcome that caused the repossession of the "old homeland" the nomads related to them stood in the way of their eternal search for the golden calf.

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THE MODERN ATON AND THE ELITES

IF WE LOOK SUFFICIENTLY BACK IN HISTORY, the global situation today will show astonishing parallels to the biblical story of Moses and along with it to the decision of the Egyptian Pharaoh Akhenaten to introduce an "all-inclusive god" named **ATON**. Both representatives were confronted with climatic change, with pests, hunger, in- and out migration, in particular with the failure of integrating citizens and immigrants.

So both tried to take recourse to an all-inclusive being, suggesting all humans were equal, because all were a copy of this one being. In the end Akhenaten's ancestors and Moses obviously shared the conclusion it would be better to accept the idea of self-responsible subunits instead of fighting continuous internal revolts. These subunits had to be separated first in mental space and then in geographic space. Monotheism failed in practice, but it has remained as a divine concept since. Akhenaten's spiritual revolution failed completely after his death, and the Hebrews after returning to Canaan, from where they originally had emigrated, could no longer tolerate those who had stayed in place.² A genocide resulted from this (Buchwald and Feingold 2012, 301, 315).³

² Judaism, Christianity and Islam are all descendants of Abraham's beliefs, i.e. they refer to Abraham in the literal and linguistic sense. Therefore, as a well-known patriarch of monotheistic religions, Abraham could have caused genocide of the Amorites much earlier than Egyptian captivity. But this did not happen. It is interesting that the ancient Hebrews did not fight the Canaanites until they came

Fig. 5. Giving of law to ancient Hebrews by Moses. An engraving of Gustave Doré.
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into contact with the Egyptians. And at that time, Egypt was a paradise of pagan cults with more than 300 deities (Bochart 1692, 204; Frazer 2012, vol. 2, 20, 26–31; Newton Yahuda Ms. 16, f. 2f–4f; Yahuda Ms. 41, f. 2r–2v, 5r; MSS.Temp3.Miss, 13). Moreover, there is a well-traced connection between the development of ancient poetry, philosophy, religion and science. This connection may result from the Egyptian captivity of Hebrews and their further Exodus (Donskikh 2019a, Essay 5).

³ Some details on dramatic changes in nature and the resulting upheavals in "history" that have shaped European consciousness to this day can be found in the historical note in the website.

Fig. 6. Akhenaton and his wife Nefertiti. Busts. The veneration of god Aton continued throughout their reign.
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Is it different nowadays in a globalised world, when elites try to convert homo sapiens into *homo billionis* and set out to substitute monotheism by mono-humanism? Those who feel they represent the “whole,” be it in the inner circles of the United Nations or on a smaller scale within the European Union, are obviously unable to see that this transcendental unification does not only fail. It triggers animosities, because individuality, the very characteristic of *homo sapiens*, is denied and declared as insubordination.

The supposed overcoming of war through a *de facto* dissolution of nations, of states and of individual religions by creating a unified global society guided by a uniform and all-embracing legislation and administration is a dystopia. It must lead to the substitution of rebellions, revolutions and asymmetric wars within a supposedly peaceful global family for state-organised wars.

The simple-minded adhering to the mantra *Keep it up!*, even worse, all that has led us to where we find ourselves now 70 years after two World wars, points to a subtle transformation of the concept and the self-awareness of the individual. In fact, it must lead to its abolition.

The idea that all men are equal and planet Earth with its pristine nature is a common habitat donated by God to man and therefore must be shared and subdued together, is nothing but hubris. Moreover, *Together we are strong!* or even *Together we are immune to any challenge, even if Nature or the Universe should try to limit us!* – this arrogant attitude throws a *mene tekel* on the concrete walls of our modern world, a *mene tekel* the dinosaurs some 65 million years ago were equally unable to interpret correctly.

REFERENCES

- Bochart, Samuel. 1692. *Geographia sacra, seu, Phaleg et Canaan: cui accedunt variae dissertationes philologicae, geographicae, theologicae, etc. antehac ineditae: ut et tabulae geographicae et indices, longè quam antea luculentiores et locupletiores.* [Sacred Geography, or Phaleg and Canaan: to Which are Added Various Dissertations of Philology and Geographic Area, the Theological Matters etc., the Unknown Past, So That the Geographic and Mapping Knowledge Might Be a Far Richer and Clearer than Ever Before]. Lugdunum: C. Boutesteyn et J. Luchtman.
<https://dl.tufts.edu/concern/pdfs/ws859t65b>
- Buchwald, Jed Z., and Mordechai Feingold. 2012. *Newton and the Origin of Civilization.* Palo Alto, CA: Princeton University Press.
- Donskikh, Oleg A. 2019a. *Essays on History and Philosophy of Science.* Novosibirsk: Novosibirsk State University of Economics and Management Press.
- Donskikh, Oleg A. 2019b. "The role of poetry in philosophy development." In *Siberian Dimension of Russian Philosophy: Schools, Branches, Traditions*, 234–236, Novosibirsk: Novosibirsk State University Press. In Russian.
- Frazer, James George, Sir. 2012. *The Golden Bough*, in 12 vols. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- MacArthur, John F. 2015. *Exodus and Numbers: The Exodus from Egypt.* Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson.
- Newton, Isaac. 1684. *Notes on ancient history and mythology.* MSS.Temp3.Miss. Library of the American Philosophical Society, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, USA.
- Newton, Isaac. 1684–1690. *Rough draft portions of and notes for "Theologiae Gentilis Origines Philosophicae" and "The Original of Monarchies".* Yahuda Ms. 16. National Library of Israel, Jerusalem, Israel.
- Newton, Isaac. Early 1690s. *Draft chapters of a treatise on the origin of religion and its corruption.* Yahuda Ms. 41. National Library of Israel, Jerusalem, Israel.
- Roberts, Scott Alan, and John Richard Ward. 2013. *The Exodus Reality: Unearthing the Real History of Moses, Identifying the Pharaohs, and Examining the Exodus from Egypt.* Pompton Plains, NJ: New Page Books.
- Sassin, Wolfgang, Donskikh, Oleg, Gnes, Alexandre, Komissarov, Sergey, and Depei Liu. 2018. *Evolutionary Environments. Homo Sapiens - an Endangered Species?* Innsbruck: Studia Universitätsverlag.

EXTENDED SUMMARY

SASSIN, WOLFGANG. DE-CREATION OF CREATION, OR A NEW LEVEL OF CULTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HOMO.

THE PRINCIPLE OF SUBDUING THE WORLD HAS SURVIVED TO OUR TIMES. In a highly elaborate form it has managed to rise above the aristocracy, the royalty and empires up to the modern "democratically" legitimised welfare state. And it has contributed to establish domestication up to the point of enslavement as the normal state of "advanced" human societies. This trend is clearly heading towards the global level. It aims at an all-embracing system of minute control of the individual, wherever he might live and how difficult it might be to "include" him. The declared objective is to maximise the total human potential by raising standards and pushing „development“, in order to be able to skim results and to distribute them "just" and global.

It is in line with this principle that ever more "powerful" economic organisations did rise and expand, particularly so once they had discovered information and communication as their most profitable field of business. This last stage of cultural "ascent" did not take millennia, however. A few start-ups emerged into global players within the last two to three decades. All societal organisations, in the entire spectrum from dictatorial to democratic, are struggling to appropriate this new instrument of "exploitation" in order to monitor "their" subjects, to control them meticulously and to skim off their "achievements," in order to further domesticate homo sapiens, unswervingly declared as "free," and to make him more "social" and "human" as a member of masses.

Does the individual have to become a cell of a "good" global organism, within perhaps one or two further generations? Is he reduced to a centrally controlled cell for the conversion of energy and information that serves a "whole" pretending to shape the planet and reaching out into space to observe everyone from above without exception? Should each of these specialised cells be activated according to a grand plan, or neutralised in the case of insubordination, if they elude the emotional and logical specifications of an autistic elite, for example because they multiply at their own discretion or seek to pursue "private" goals?

With using historical examples of Hebrew exodus from Egypt, Moses and Akhenaten, the author advances the notion of mono-humanism and develops a theory of transformation of monotheism to mono-humanism. Within this theory, he discusses if we are entering the era of a global culture which sets out to dissolve all forms of existing cultures, from hunting and gathering, via locally and regionally adapted farming to industrial production depending on highly unequally distributed natural exhaustible and renewable resources. The author discusses the possibilities of our facing a *Hybrid Society* in which a *Big Brother*, realised in the form of algorithms and a densely networked communication infrastructure, an omnipresent two-way "social media system," will determine what each human being, an "individual cell" would have to do and to avoid, including its sacrifice if it is necessary. The trend towards the dissolution of all kinds of borders, the dissolution of cultural niches, even the conviction that there is a "right" acquired by birth to participate in this crease-free, i.e. simple-minded paradise

with standardised living conditions, taken together they characterise the post-modern Western *Zeitgeist*. It ignores the resulting indispensable necessity of such an "organism" to force each „cell" to specialize on command and to remain on the spot and to willingly fulfil the "function" it has been assigned to in one of the different organs of the "whole." Every functional and spatial deviation of such a "cell" from its place would then be equivalent to "migration" and to the formation of "parallel societies," terms that are known in the medical field as proliferation and metastasis of "autonomous" cancerous cells.

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